

Revised Interpretation of Gravitational Tidal Waves (Plus Mass-from-Gravity Concept) Introduces New Ideas Regarding Breakup of Celestial Bodies, Earth's Ocean Tides, Big Bang, Eternal Life, World Peace and Matter or Mass

Abstract -

This article had its beginning with Einstein's 1919 paper "Do gravitational fields play an essential role in the structure of elementary particles?" Together with General Relativity's statement that gravity is not a pull but is a push caused by the curvature of space-time, a hypothesis for Earth's ocean tides was developed that does not solely depend on the Sun and Moon as Kepler and Newton believed. It also borrows from Galileo. The breakup of planets and asteroids by white dwarfs, neutron stars or black holes is popularly ascribed by today's science to tidal forces (gravitation emanating from the stellar body and having a greater effect on the near side of a planet/asteroid than the farthest side). Remembering General Relativity, it was apparent that my revised idea of tidal forces improves on current accounts because it views matter and mass as unified with space-time whose curvature is gravitation. Unification is a necessity for modern science's developing view of one united and entangled universe – expressed in the Unified Field Theory, the Theory of Everything, String theory and Loop Quantum Gravity. The writing of this article was also assisted by visualizing the gravitational fields forming space-time being themselves formed by a multitude of weak and presently undetectable gravitational waves. The final part of this article concludes that the section **BITS AND TOPOLOGY** will lead to the conclusions in **ETERNAL LIFE, WORLD PEACE AND PHYSICS' UNIFICATION**. The final part also compares gravitation and electromagnetism to biological enzymes while biology's substrate of reacting "chemicals" is the Mobius strip plus the figure-8 Klein bottle. The product is mass and enzyme, substrate and product are all considered mathematical in nature.

CELESTIAL TIDES

Figure 1 – BIDIRECTIONALITY OF, AND REFRESHING BY, GRAVITATION

(drawn by author using Microsoft's "Paint" program)

If gravity is a pull from Earth's centre, its effect on surface crust that has been heated and made mobile would be to pull it directly downwards toward the centre without any sideways deviation (apparent stretching). But if gravity follows Einstein's General Relativity theory, it'd be a push caused by the local curvature of space-time. The gravitational waves in this curvature would strike the crust from all angles. Some come vertically from directly above, pushing it down and causing flattening. Other waves come obliquely from very low angles, giving the heated and mobile crust a nearly horizontal push and resulting in sideways deviation (apparent stretching). Such interaction with matter implies that gravity does not simply penetrate everything but is absorbed and re-radiated. It also says "yes" to the question asked by Einstein's 1919 paper "Do gravitational fields play an essential role in the structure of elementary particles?" (the paper also speaks of electromagnetism – implying that electromagnetism is the other contributor to mass). (1)

If enough gravitational waves travelling from outside the solar system to the stellar body are absorbed then re-emitted, they could alter gravitational fields and push the planet away. If a star only received the input of gravitational waves from deep space entering it, there would be no limit to its potential growth. Since it also radiates mass-forming gravitational waves, there is a limit to the growth. 99% of the solar system's mass / gravitational waves / gravity are associated with our star, so the gravitational push on Earth from the solar sphere may be slightly greater than the push from the waves originating from deep space on the other side of the solar system. The gravitational fields and waves from deep space would exert a push on a body and are a possible

unrecognized contributing factor to the Pioneer anomaly, where the Pioneer spacecraft near the solar system's edge are a few thousand kilometres closer to the Sun than predicted. The re-emission of gravity by the Sun could be misinterpreted as gravity originating within the Sun and exerting a pull which keeps planets in orbit (this neglects the gravitational push coming from regions of space opposite the Sun). In the end, our planet's orbit would be growing slowly larger. There is a science paper that concludes the distance between Sun and Earth is growing by approx. 15 centimetres per century. (2) The two authors attribute this increase of the AU or Astronomical Unit (AU = the average distance between Earth and the Sun) to dark energy. As this article has shown, the increase may be gravitational.

In the diagram above, the different parts of the planet/moon/asteroid are accelerated – waves and fields from the left attempt to push it to refreshment position A (the word "refresh" is taken from computers and means the updating of the celestial body's display). Gravity does more than try to relocate the body to A: it also attempts to re-form the body at A. Simultaneously, waves and fields from the right attempt to push it to (and reform it at) refreshment position B. The stresses resulting from being reformed at A and B at the same time are the cause of the planet's/asteroid's being torn apart. Though this disintegration can occur in any stellar system, it's more likely to happen in a system dominated by a white dwarf or neutron star or black hole ie a system where a multitude of powerful waves/fields contribute to the great mass at the centre and create intense gravitation in all regions.

Reorienting of all astronomical orbits is inevitable in the long run (unless prevented by intervention) because gravitational waves and fields are dynamic and constantly changing. This article's revision of tidal forces is similar to the currently accepted model. But instead of focusing on gravitation from the stellar body being a pull that has a greater effect on the near side of a planet/asteroid than the farthest side, it states that a celestial body's breakup results from gravitation being pushes from opposite directions.

OCEAN TIDES

How, then, can repelling or pushing gravity account for the apparent attraction of ocean tides towards the Moon? I believe such an idea of gravity requires the idea of 17th-century scientists Isaac Newton and Johannes Kepler that the moon causes the tides, to be joined with Galileo's idea that the Earth's movements slosh its water.

"If a barge (carrying a cargo of freshwater) suddenly ground to a halt on a sandbar, for instance, the water pushed up towards the bow then bounced back toward the stern, doing this several times with ever decreasing agitation until it returned to a level state. Galileo realized that the Earth's dual motion—its daily one around its axis and its annual one around the sun—might have the same effect on oceans and other great bodies of water as the barge had on its freshwater cargo." (3)

Gravity's apparent attraction can be summarized by the following - gravitation is absorbed into wave packets and the inertia of the gravitons (united with far more energetic photons) carries objects towards Earth's centre at 9.8 m/s or 32 ft/s. The mass of the oceans on Earth is estimated at nearly 1.5 billion cubic kilometres. (4) All this water is being pushed towards Earth's centre at 32 feet per second every second. But the seafloor prevents its descent. So there is a recoil, noticeable offshore (it is only where oceans and continents meet that tides are great enough to be noticed). This recoil is larger during the spring tides seen at full and new moon because sun, Earth and moon are aligned at these times.

The previous paragraph's alignment of Sun, Earth and moon therefore refers to their being lined up where the gravitational current is greatest (in the plane where planets and moons are created) - and to more of the gravitational waves travelling from the outer solar system being captured by solar and lunar wave packets, and less of them being available on Earth to suppress oceanic recoil (there are still enough to maintain the falling-bodies rate of 32 feet per second per second). At the neap tides of 1st and 3rd quarter; the sun, earth and moon aren't lined up but form a right angle and our planet has access to more gravity waves, which suppress oceanic recoil to a greater degree. We can imagine the sun and moon pulling earth's water in different directions at neap tide but suppression is a more accurate description. If variables like wind/atmospheric pressure/storms are deleted, this greater suppression causes neap tides which are much lower than spring tides.

Figure 2 – TIDE SCHEMATIC

public domain image from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Tide_schematic.svg

After absorption (whether in oceans, in space, or anywhere else), the gravitational waves are used in refreshing mass plus, possibly, the strong and weak nuclear forces associated with matter. This refers to theories where the role of the mass-giving Higgs field is fulfilled by particular couplings (5). (In this case, the couplings are of gravitation/electromagnetism and, as explained in the next paragraph, the Mobius/Klein). They would act like a cosmic catalyst – similar to the biological catalysts called enzymes - accelerating the refreshing of mass without undergoing any permanent change themselves. They are then re-radiated from stars, planets, interstellar gas and dust, etc as gravitational waves (a Gravity Wave Background, challenging the idea that the traditional form of Cosmic Inflation was necessary to generate gravitational waves). The associated electromagnetism filling space-time, mass and matter is also re-radiated as all types of electromagnetic waves: including an infrared background whose heat output exceeds that of the stars alone, in addition to a microwave background. The latter challenges the idea that existence of the cosmic microwave background proves the universe began with the Big Bang.

BITS AND TOPOLOGY

Continuing with the analogy of gravitation and electromagnetism [for convenience, this coupling will be denoted in this paragraph by lower-case (a)] to biology's enzyme: what would then be the substrate - the reacting "molecules" (a) "binds to" and "holds in the proper position" to form the product, mass (m)? A condensed extract from a previous article of mine (6) will now show how the substrate could be the Mobius strip (which incorporates Wick rotation) plus the figure-8 Klein bottle [a coupling referred to by (b)].

Stephen Hawking writes, "What the spin of a particle really tells us is what the particle looks like from different directions." (7) Particles of matter like the proton and electron have spin $1/2$, which means these particles must be turned through two complete revolutions to look the same – and, not coincidentally, you must go around a Mobius strip twice to reach your starting point. It seems plausible that the particular values of quantum spin could be determined by another set of particular values viz those in electronics' BITS or Binary digITS, which always take the form of either 1 or 0. First, the 1's and 0's are programmed to form the shape of a Mobius strip, which is merely two-dimensional (2-D).

Figure 3 - MOBIUS STRIP (source: http://www.clker.com/cliparts/3/7/a/9/1220546534781713951lummie_Mobius_Strip.svg_hi.png)

Then two strips must be joined to make a 4-D Klein bottle (8) which has length, width, depth and, when Wick rotation is programmed into the strips as a subroutine (see Figure 5), the 4th dimension of movement in time. The type of Klein bottle formed would appear to be the figure-8 Klein. A diagram of many figure-8 Klein bottles would show that their positive curvature (on the spherical parts) fits together with their negative curvature (on saddle-shaped parts) to cancel and produce, on a cosmic scale, the flat curvature of space-time (9). When you have trillions of Mobius and figure-8 Klein

elements assembled, you can follow the theory of the mass-giving Higgs field being the result of various couplings. An implication of a 1919 paper by Einstein is that the coupling is between gravitons and photons. With trillions of Mobius and figure-8 Klein elements assembled, an appropriate number of photons and gravitons must be included to give the matter what we call the emergent property of mass - similar to hydrogen and oxygen combining to give water what we call wetness. (Subatomic particles must possess quantum mechanical wave-particle duality if they're composed of gravitational plus electromagnetic waves. Duality also says waves possess particle-like properties ie the waves are composed of gravitons and photons – and duality is necessary for matter to be included in spacetime unification.)

Figure 4 - MOBIUS DOUBLET (FIGURE-8 KLEIN BOTTLE) (source: <https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/7/73/KleinBottle-Figure8-01.png>) Note that, when considering many bottles, the reddish positive curvature fits together with the bluish negative curvature to produce the flatness implying space-time's infinity and, since space and time are always unified, its eternity. (In flat space-time, light beams travel in straight lines and can go infinite distance without ever meeting.)

SUPERSYMMETRY AND WICK ROTATION

Following Albert Einstein's example of turning Max Planck's quanta (which, for years, Planck and all other scientists considered purely mathematical) into explanation of the physical photoelectric effect, the Wick rotation used to describe imaginary time may be transformed from mathematical "trickery" to physical meaning, and provide a modern way to unite space and time into one space-time.

Figure 5 – WICK ROTATION: "The complex plane reveals i 's special relationship with cycles via the circle of i , also known as Wick rotation. Whenever a point on the complex plane is multiplied by i , it moves a quarter rotation around the origin or center of the plane." (Figure and quote from 10)

Supersymmetry (SUSY) proposes a relationship between bosons and fermions. Some scientists believe supersymmetry is a failed theory. A new approach would be proposing that the Mobius strip is a fundamental constituent of both fermions and bosons - and therefore unites all particles (of matter and of energy) into one **space**. The inner and outer surfaces of a Mobius form a continuous strip in space – unification of space with time requires a temporal continuity. This is carried out by Wick rotation's continuous cycling between what are called real and imaginary **time** (on the horizontal x-axis and vertical y-axis, respectively) – a property programmed into the Mobius strip. Therefore, the Mobius strip combined with Wick rotation and imaginary time provides a modern way to unite space and time (and imaginary space-time's "dark matter") into one **space-time**. (The continuously curved Mobius surface + continuous Wick rotation = curvature of space-time.)

^ In a science TV program, (11) Dr. Graham Phillips reported that "the physicist and writer Paul Davies thinks the universe is indeed fine-tuned for minds like ours. And who fine-tuned it? Not God but minds from the future, perhaps even our distant descendants, that have reached back through time ... and selected the very laws of physics that allow for the existence of minds in the first place. Sounds bizarre, but quantum physics actually allows that kind of thing."

ETERNAL LIFE, WORLD PEACE AND PHYSICS' UNIFICATION

My beliefs are based on science's search for a theory uniting everything on Earth, in space and in time. For a brief history of unification from scientist Hermann Weyl's unification scheme and Albert Einstein's Unified Field Theory to modern physics' string theory and Theory of Everything, see reference 12. Though we see things as separate, we'll ultimately understand that the universe is just one thing – like the objects in a computer image seem to be a lot of separate objects but are really just one thing (strings of binary digits – see **BITS AND TOPOLOGY**). Defying our bodily senses (which are limited and subject to illusions), every person is united by these strings of binary digits. We can, if we wish, express this as – you and I are the same person in many ways. When people realize that hurting others in any manner is the same as hurting yourself, the Golden Rule (treat others as you would like to be treated yourself) will spring to life and world peace will be inevitable.

Returning to eternal life - certainly, the bodies we have now won't last forever and will die sooner or later. My belief that we go on has nothing at all to do with the idea of the soul or spirit. I believe science's search for unification will be successful and as long as the universe continues, you and I will go on in some form because we're part of it. When his engineer friend Michele Angelo Besso died, Albert Einstein wrote a letter of condolence to the Besso family, including his now famous quote: 'Now he has departed from this strange world a little ahead of me. That means nothing. People like us, who believe in physics, know that the distinction between past, present and future is only a stubbornly persistent illusion.' This suggests the following interpretation of his statement - if someone is alive in what we call the present, they must continue to be alive at any point in the future, all points of which have no actual separation from the present (though that future life would not be in the form we know). So there would be life after death. If all times in the past are united with the present, there must also be life before conception (in a different form, possibly the same as that existing after death).

COSMIC ENZYME AND SUBSTRATE

Gravitation and electromagnetism (coupling a) "binds to" and "holds in the proper position" the Mobius strip (which incorporates Wick rotation) plus the figure-8 Klein bottle (coupling b). It does this by uniting two Mobius strips to form each figure-8 Klein bottle. (a) also changes the shape of the figure-8 Klein bottle. Informally - if an object in space consists of one piece and does not have any "holes" that pass all the way through it, it is called simply connected. A doughnut (and the figure-8 Klein bottle it resembles) is "holey" and not simply connected (they're multiply connected). Referring to the infinite universe (see text associated with Figure 4) - a flat universe that is also simply connected implies an infinite universe [13]. So it seems the infinite universe cannot be composed of subunits called figure-8 Klein bottles (flat universes that are finite in extent include the torus and Klein bottle). But the changing of the Klein bottle's shape by gravitation and electromagnetism mimics the process of gaps in, or irregularities between, figure-8 Klein bottles being "filled in" by binary digits in the same way that computer drawings can extrapolate a small patch of blue sky to make a sky that's blue from horizon to horizon. This ensures the positive and negative shapes in different figure-8 Klein bottles are precisely united, and makes space-time relatively smooth and continuous as Einstein thought. Plus - it gets rid of holes, making figure-8 Klein subunits feasible.

Though (a)'s waves are re-radiated, mass can remain constant because new waves are perpetually absorbed and re-emitted, renewing and refreshing the mass. Since the elements in (b) are both mathematical shapes, (a) must also be mathematical to interact with it. It uses the base-2 maths of BITS (BInary digITS) to produce $m = (a) (b)$.

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